

Maximizer Students Exert More Effort but are Less Satisfied

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Abstract

Inspired by prior groundbreaking studies on maximizing by Simon and other researchers, we sought to see whether the findings extend to lower-stakes decision-making. The particular lower-stakes context we chose to study is class selection by college students. We examined the relationships between maximizing tendency and four variables: information-seeking behavior, efforting behavior, regret affect, satisfaction affect. We had 130 different participants (64% female, 32% male, 4% other) from three semesters of a particular Psychology class at a university. The participants took an online questionnaire, which measured their maximizing tendency, behaviors, and affects related directly to our investigation. Through correlation tests, we found that maximizing was positively correlated with information-seeking ($r = .34, p < .001$), with efforting ($r = .37, p < .001$), and with regret ($r = .23, p = .01$); maximizing was negatively correlated on the outcome satisfaction variable ($r = -.19, p = .03$). With a Median Split and independent samples t-tests, we found that maximizers score higher in every area except on outcome satisfaction, where we did not find any result statistically significant. Our findings suggest there is a relationship between maximizing and the aforesaid behaviors and affects.

Keywords: maximizing, satisficing

Introduction

We observe that some people seek the superlative in making a decision: when picking a restaurant, planning a vacation, for examples. In contrast, some others simply stop when they find an option they consider "good enough" -- to go along with the previous example, they stop when the restaurant looks acceptable, or a vacation that gives them the minimum of what they want. We found literature that have both studied these behaviors and established terminology to describe the styles of decision-making.

Herbert Simon (1956) defined satisficing as a behavior that stops when it finds satisfaction for all its needs in the stead of seeking something even better. Schwartz et al. (2002) further separate people that satisfice from those that maximize: maximizers are people that pursue the best outcome. In a groundbreaking paper, Schwartz published a Maximization Scale (MS) he developed to define and measure a person's tendency to maximize. With this scale that Schwartz developed, Iyengar et al. (2006) performed a longitudinal, correlational study and found that maximizing were positively related to better outcomes, but also was associated with negative affect.

However, researchers have disagreed on how maximizing is operationalized. For instance, Diab et al. (2008) proposed their own scale to measure maximizing tendency. They argued that their Maximizing Tendency Scale is both simpler and more internally valid. (Diab et al. asserted a higher Cronbach's alpha -- a measure of a scale's internal validity -- and touted their focus on defining maximizing as the pursuit of the best outcome, arguing that Schwartz's operationalization of the maximizing tendency had an effect on their results as it did not measure just maximizing tendency itself.)

In the arena of maximizing vs satisficing, we did not find any literature that examined whether heretofore findings extend to what can be considered less-major decisions, such as selecting courses at one's college. Will the findings presented by currently available literature extend to college students in the context of course selection?

To answer those questions is the purpose of the study. More specifically, our aim in this study is to examine whether the maximizing tendencies documented in aforementioned literature exist solely in the domain of high-consequent choices. In other words, do the patterns extend to lower-stakes decision contexts, namely college course selection. In that context, we investigate the relationship between maximizing tendencies and four variables: those four variables are information-seeking behavior, efforting behavior, regret affect, and satisfaction (with outcome) affect.

We have four hypotheses. In the first one, we predict maximizing and information-seeking behavior will be correlated positively: if people are maximizers, then they will seek more information (e.g. from reviews or from peers). In our second hypothesis, we predict that maximizing and effort behavior will be correlated positively: if the students are maximizers, then they will spend more effort in selecting their courses. In our third hypothesis, we predict that maximizing are related to negative affect: if people are maximizers, then they will experience more regret. And in our fourth hypothesis, we predict that maximizing will have a negative correlation with outcome satisfaction: if people are maximizers, then they will have lower satisfaction with their outcome.

Methods

Participants

Participants are the students of a particular Psychology class. They were required to complete a survey online as a class assignment. In the survey, they answered questions about their course selection. Participants come from three different semesters: we are combining three different cross-sectional samples, not using time as an Independent Variable.

There are 130 participants: 45 from Spring 2025 (35%), 12 from Summer '24 (9%), and 73 from Spring '24 (56%). Of these, 83 are female (64%), 42 are male (32%), 5 are non-binary or prefer-not-to-say (4%). Age ranges from 19-52 ($M=24.5$, $SD=6.2$). They come across the schools of the University: 65 from the School of General Studies, 53 from Columbia College, 9 from the School of Professional Studies, 1 from the Jewish Theological Seminary, 1 from Barnard College, 1 from the Graduate School of Arts and Sciences. Furthermore, 8 are sophomores, 61 are juniors, 50 are seniors, 9 are post-bac.

At this point we would like to report the t-test for two gender groups. To test whether there were gender differences in maximizing tendencies, we conducted a t-test to examine the mean difference participants that identify as males ($M = 5.04$, $SD = 1.05$) with those that identify as females ($M = 4.79$, $SD = .95$). However, the difference was not significant ($t(123) = -1.35$, $p = .18$).

The study was approved by our IRB.

Materials and Procedures

The material consists only of an online questionnaire given in the semester's first two weeks. The survey takes less than 30 minutes to complete. The questionnaire takes the student through its four sections. The first section that the student see is Maximizing Scale (Schwartz, 2002). Here they complete 13 questions, each giving a 1 if they strongly disagree and 7 when

they strongly agree. Some of the items are "No matter what I do, I have the highest standards for myself," and "I often fantasize about living in ways that are quite different from my actual life." Their scores (1-7) are averaged among the 13 questions, giving us their MS maximizing score.

In the next part, the student gives their gender, age, major, school, and year. Then, the student meets 17 questions. These items also ask for a number 1-7 (7 for strongly agree), and the questions are grouped into four: how much information the student seeks (e.g. "I ask my peers for advice about which courses to take"), the amount of effort they expend (e.g. "I spend a lot of time and effort thinking about which classes to take"), their regret (e.g. "I wish I had more flexibility so I could take different classes"), and their outcome satisfaction (e.g. "I wish I had enrolled in different courses this semester").

In the last part, the student completes the Maximizing Tendency Scale, a scale which comprises 9 questions, each requiring a 1-7, where 7 indicates strongly agree. These questions focus on identifying the tendency to seek the best option, with items such as "No matter what it takes, I always try to choose the best thing", and "I will wait for the best option, no matter how long it takes".

Correlation Tests (with Pearson's r)

Then, for each of the four measures (info-seeking, effort, regret, satisfaction), we perform correlations test against maximizing score. We do this to see whether there is a statistically-significant correlation between the maximizing tendency score and the measurement for the behavior or affect.

T-Tests

After the correlations, we separated the maximizers and the satisficers using a Median Split on the MTS scale. Those whose maximizing scores are above the median of the entire sample are categorized as Maximizers, and the rest are Satisficers. We want to compare if the means in the behavior and affect scores are higher -- or lower -- among one group.

Results

On Maximizing and Information-Seeking Behavior

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between information-seeking behavior ($M = 4.66$, $SD = 1.11$) and maximizing tendency ($M = 4.89$, $SD = .98$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between information-seeking and maximizing was found to be weak and statistically significant, $r(128) = .34$, $p < .001$. These results suggest that the behavior of information-seeking and the tendency to maximize are positively related weakly, with information-seeking increasing with maximizing tendency.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in information-seeking between maximizers ($M = 4.97$, $SD = .92$) and satisficers ($M = 4.41$, $SD = 1.18$). There was a significant effect, $t(128) = 2.94$, $p = .004$, such that maximizers received higher scores than satisficers. This result suggests that maximizers tend to seek out more information than satisficers do.

On Maximizing and Efforting Behavior

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between efforting behavior ($M = 4.43$, $SD = 1.23$) and maximizing score ($M = 4.89$, $SD = .98$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation

between efforting and maximizing was found to be weak and statistically significant, $r(128) = .37, p < .001$. These results suggest that efforting and maximizing are positively related weakly, with efforting behavior increasing with maximizing tendency.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in efforting between maximizers ($M = 4.73, SD = 1.03$) and satisficers ($M = 4.18, SD = 1.33$). There was a significant effect, $t(128) = 2.58, p = .01$, such that maximizers received higher scores than satisficers. This result suggests that maximizers tend to exert more effort than do satisficers.

On Maximizing and Regret Affect

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between the regret affect ($M = 4.86, SD = 1.52$) and maximizing tendency ($M = 4.89, SD = .98$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between information-seeking and maximizing was found to be weak and statistically significant, $r(128) = .23, p = .01$. These results suggest that the affect of regret and the tendency to maximize are positively related weakly, with regret increasing with maximizing.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in regret between maximizers ($M = 5.16, SD = 1.36$) and satisficers ($M = 4.63, SD = 1.60$). There was a significant effect, $t(128) = 1.97, p = .049$, such that maximizers received higher scores than satisficers. This result suggest that maximizers tend to exhibit more regret than satisficers.

On Maximizing and Satisfaction Affect

Correlations

A Pearson correlation addressed the relationship between satisfaction affect ($M = 5.25$, $SD = 1.43$) and maximizing tendency ($M = 4.89$, $SD = .98$). For an alpha level of .05, the correlation between satisfaction with outcome and maximizing tendency was found to be very weak and statistically significant, $r(128) = -.19$, $p = .03$. These results suggest that the affect of being satisfied with the outcome of one's efforts and one's tendency to maximize are negatively related though very weakly so, with satisfaction decreasing with maximizing.

T-tests

A t-test examined the mean difference in satisfaction between maximizers ($M = 5.09$, $SD = 1.54$) and satisficers ($M = 5.39$, $SD = 1.34$). There was not a significant effect, $t(128) = -1.20$, $p = .23$, such that this result is not statistically significant.

Discussion

To summarize, we have investigated the relationship between maximizing tendencies and four variables among students in selecting college courses. Those four variables are information-seeking behavior, efforting behavior, regret affect, and satisfaction (with outcome) affect. What we found were statistically significant and supported our hypotheses. We found that the behavior of information-seeking was positively correlated with maximizing tendency; and, we found -- with statistical significance -- that maximizers demonstrated higher levels of information-seeking than satisficers. On the second variable, we also found that maximizing and efforting are positively correlated; we found that maximizers tend to exert more effort than satisficers do. On the first of the two affect variables, we found that maximizing was positively correlated with regret; in the t-test, we found that maximizers exhibited more regret than do satisficers.

On the second of the two affect variables, which was also the last of the four variables we examined, we found the correlation test supportive of our hypothesis. But, the t-tests told us there was no effect ($p = .23$). Overall, these findings support our hypotheses, and they have extended our previous knowledge on maximizing into the domain of college course selection.

The patterns observed by previous literature have been observed among our participants in their choices of what classes to take. Students with maximizing tendencies engage in information-seeking and efforting behaviors in forming their decisions -- consistent with the established theories explored by Simon (1956) in his contexts. The affects of regret and satisfaction levels proposed in the context of consumer decisions by Schwartz et al. (2002) are also observed among our participants: we found positive correlation between maximizing and regret, and negative correlation between maximizing and satisfaction. As such, we could say that our predictions -- which were based on these previous studies -- were confirmed.

Thus, we may assert that our study -- which by the way employed both correlational tests and t-tests -- has made an important contribution to the literature on maximizing. That contribution is that, we have demonstrated that maximizing patterns do extend into the context of college students selecting what courses to take -- a domain that had not been studied before. This is significant, not just because ours is the first study that looks into our particular domain, but also because course decision may be considered a "more minor" or "less major" decision than, for example, a career choice would be.

Nonetheless, our study has limitations. For instance, despite our converging evidence, we are not making claims of causation: such claims would be unfounded. The next limitation is our sample, which consists of students from one certain Psychology class at one particular university

-- one may argue how generalizable our findings are to the rest of the context of college course selection.

To address these limitations, future studies may obtain a random sample of students from more than just one class and beyond just one university. Or, another possible future study may be a longitudinal one to see whether the patterns are the same throughout the student's college years, or is there another variable that may influence the patterns we've seen associated with maximizing.

But, despite its limitations, our study lends support to the generalizing claim that maximizing tendencies cut across different domains of decision making. The patterns associated with maximizing -- particularly these: exerting much resources in seeking information and efforting, experiencing greater regret, and less satisfaction, etc -- are observed also in lower-stakes decisions (namely the college course selection) that we observed.

In summary, our study provides converging evidence that maximizing patterns extend beyond consumer purchases and career choices to lower-stakes decisions, represented by course selection by college students. Our study shows how participants invest more resources in seeking information and efforting, yet experience greater regret and less satisfaction -- patterns found previously in other domains by other researchers. The consistency in how these patterns are observed across larger and smaller decisions suggests that maximizing may be a stable trait that is involved in any decision-making process.

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